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Determination Of Physicochemical Properties Of Water From Boreholes In Southern Delta And Their Health Implications

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ABSTRACT

Of the various means of sustenance, water take a unique role. Without it many forms of life would either not exist or perish. It is an important aspect when it comes to growth; so also when it comes to types of food, means of making the food and health implications behind its consumption. There are different sources of water, however the one obtained through borehole from aquifers is a unique way of getting domestic and drinking water; hence the need for this study in Delta State to determine their level of heavy metals concentrations. Of interest were Warri metropolis where there is College of Education Warri (COEW); and Ethiope axis where we have College of Education Mosogar (COEM). Both areas are located in the southern part of Delta State, having soil formation known for water percolation and leaching throughout the year. Twenty borehole samples were investigated; with ten from COEW and COEM respectively. The physical parameters determined were hydrogen ion concentration (pH), electrical conductivity (EC), turbidity, colour and odour; while the chemical parameter, which are mainly heavy metals, were Cd, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn. The physical parameters were determined using known conventional methods while the chemical parameters were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometer after the samples have been digested. For the physical parameters, the pH, EC, turbidity, odour and colour were okay for all the samples; while alkalinity were higher in borehole in most of the samples. All the samples were not turbid, colourless and odourless. When the results obtained were compared with WHO, USEPA and NESREA standards for the heavy metals analysed, Cd, Cr, Co and Mn were all below detectable level (.001 ppm). Values obtained for Zn shows that they were within permissible limit; while most values obtained for Ni were also within permissible limit for the three standards. On the other hand, the values obtained for Cu and Fe indicated high concentrations that were far above the employed standards; while Pb values were even astronomical; far above the permissible limits for WHO, USEPA and NESREA standards. This shows the need for the treatment of water from these boreholes so as to avert any health complications resulting from their consumption since they are utilised for drinking, domestic and other purposes.

Keywords: borehole, aquifers, water

, water

INTRODUCTION

Water is of much important to the survival of living things and is a resources which influences human life. Generally, water is obtained from mainly two types of natural sources, they are surface water which include lakes, ponds, rivers, streams, etc. And ground water; which consist of bore holes and well water.

Water plays an important role in domestic, industrial, irrigation and other processes all over the world. However, population explosion, industrialization and urbanization have caused a lot of havoc which result in contamination of ground water. Contaminated ground water is not easy to restore, hence it is necessary to protect the quality of ground water. According to World Health Organisation (WHO) report, 80% of diseases arises due to contamination of ground water (Izah *et al.*, 2016).

Groundwater is the principal natural water resources for both drinking, domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes. Nowadays one of the most important environmental issues is groundwater contamination. In areas where population density is high and human use of the land is intensive, groundwater becomes vulnerable. Virtually any activity whereby chemicals or wastes may be released to the environment, either intentionally or accidentally, has the potential to pollute groundwater. When ground water becomes contaminated, it becomes an issue on different level because it becomes difficult and expensive to carry out clean up (Eid *et al.*, 2016; Balogun *et al.*, 2021).

Water is a universal solvent and is one of the most commonly available natural resources of man which makes up about 70% of man's body. Heavy metals on the other hand can be defined as "metals with densities that are five times heavier than water and are formed naturally from the terrestrial environments, and they are found in rocks, plants, soils and sediments" (Iwar *et al.*, 2021). The works of man and his industries have tendencies to increase the quantity of heavy metals in the environment, which favours environmental degradation (Ubwa *et al.*, 2013).

Heavy metals are among the major contaminants of groundwater sources. Some of these heavy metals are essential for the growth, development and health of living organisms, whereas others are non-essential as they are indestructible and most of them are categorized as toxic species on organisms. Nonetheless, the toxicity of heavy metals depends on their concentration levels in the environment. With increasing concentrations in environment and decreasing the capacity of soils toward retaining heavy metals, they leach into groundwater and soil solution. Thus, these toxic heavy metals can be accumulated in living tissues and concentrate through the food chain (Balogun *et al.*, 2021; Ataikiru *et al.*, 2025).

Heavy metals pollution of water generally has become a major environmental problem, especially since the advent of mechanised agriculture and industrial revolution; and today most water resources are still being contaminated with heavy metals released from domestic, industrial and other man-made activities. The threat of toxic and trace metals in the environment is more serious than those of other pollutants due to their non-biodegradable nature, accumulative properties and long biological half-lives. It is difficult to remove them completely from the environment once they enter into it. Heavy metal contamination may have devastating impacts on the ecological balance of natural water bodies including the loss of aquatic diversity. With increased use of a wide variety of metals in industries and in our daily life, there is now a greater awareness of toxic metal pollution of the environment. Many of these metals tend to remain in the ecosystem and eventually move from one compartment to the other within the food chain (Vardhan, 2019; Balogun *et al.*, 2023).

Fish are often at the top of aquatic food chain and when pollutants build up in the food chain, fish are widely used to evaluate the health of aquatic ecosystems. Fish may concentrate large amounts of metals from the water and therefore are responsible for adverse effects and death in the environment. The concern about the high levels of trace metals in foods has prompted several statutory bodies such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) to establish maximum tolerable concentrations allowed for some of these metals in food and aquatic organisms. Thus World Health Organization (WHO) as well as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) made it mandatory to monitor eight elements in fish species. They are Hg, Cd, Pb, As, Cu, Zn, Fe and Sn. This is obligatory, while the monitoring of others, though not obligatory, but may be useful and important (Tongesayi *et al.*, 2014).

Industrial development and uncontrolled increase of rural-urban migration has led to the growth of the urban population and this have resulted in increase in waste ranging from industrial to municipal, which have adverse effects on human populace. Hence the need to study and evaluate some of these heavy metals concentration in ground water within Delta State, using tertiary institutions in the state as the main focus. Most of these institutions were built in areas that were formally used for various purposes such as industrial, military post, refuse dump, agriculture, to mention but a few; thus anthropogenic factors may

play a vital role in their contamination, if the results shows ground water contamination, since these areas are known for rainfall almost throughout the year and as a result, there is percolation and leaching due to the nature of the soil and formation. Additionally, in recent, waste disposal systems and management are way more advanced than it was in the past since modern techniques and facilities are now being employed in the collection, dumping, recollection and recycling of these waste hence the need to move with time so as to minimise ground water contamination and its bitter consequences (Balogun et al., 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Samples

Twenty samples of water from boreholes were collected from the premises of College of Education, Warri (COEW) and College of Education, Mosogar (COEM). College of Education at Warri is having about twenty-two (22) water boreholes while College of Education at Mosogar is having about sixteen (16) water boreholes. The water samples were collected in clean sample bottle; which were finally rinsed with the sample to be stored in them before collection. Ten (10) samples were collected from COEW from ten different boreholes. Also, ten (10) samples were collected from COEM from ten different boreholes. The twenty water samples were coded and treated to prevent decomposition. They were then kept in a cool, clean and safe laboratory tight cupboard before digestion. College of Education Warri samples were coded CWBW-1 to CWBW-10; while those collected from College of Education Mosogar were coded CMBW-1 to CMBW-10.

Table 1: List of Coded Samples from College of Education, Warri

SN	Sample Code	Coordinate
1	CWBW-1	Lat 5.323571 ⁰ N; Long 5.443663 ⁰ E
2	CWBW-2	Lat 5.322294 ⁰ N; Long 5.443811 ⁰ E
3	CWBW-3	Lat 5.322174 ⁰ N; Long 5.444167 ⁰ E
4	CWBW-4	Lat 5.322965 ⁰ N; Long 5.443980 ⁰ E
5	CWBW-5	Lat 5.323550 ⁰ N; Long 5.443671 ⁰ E
6	CWBW-6	Lat 5.322931 ⁰ N; Long 5.443662 ⁰ E
7	CWBW-7	Lat 5.323115 ⁰ N; Long 5.443407 ⁰ E
8	CWBW-8	Lat 5.321987 ⁰ N; Long 5.443995 ⁰ E
10	CWBW-9	Lat 5.323272 ⁰ N; Long 5.442941 ⁰ E

Table 2: List of Coded Samples from College of Education, Mosogar

SN	Sample Point	Coordinate
1	CMBW-1	Lat 5.906927 ⁰ N; Long 5.742982 ⁰ E
2	CMBW-2	Lat 5.909248 ⁰ N; Long 5.741008 ⁰ E
3	CMBW-3	Lat 5.904979 ⁰ N; Long 5.740678 ⁰ E
4	CMBW-4	Lat 5.905291 ⁰ N; Long 5.742324 ⁰ E
5	CMBW-5	Lat 5.908919 ⁰ N; Long 5.741008 ⁰ E
6	CMBW-6	Lat 5.904641 ⁰ N; Long 5.741666 ⁰ E
7	CMBW-7	Lat 5.904959 ⁰ N; Long 5.742653 ⁰ E
8	CMBW-8	Lat 5.906927 ⁰ N; Long 5.742982 ⁰ E
9	CMBW-9	Lat 5.911355 ⁰ N; Long 5.749526 ⁰ E
10	CMBW-10	Lat 5.898804 ⁰ N; Long 5.734096 ⁰ E

Sample Preparation

Digestions were carried out using available standard procedures. USEPA Method 3050B (USEPA, 1996) and method reported in Radojevic and Bashkin (1999) were used to carry out the digestion of these water samples. 5 mL of each water sample was measured into a 250 mL flat bottom conical flask using standard measuring cylinder. To each sample was added 10 mL of 10% trioxonitrate (V) acid (HNO₃) and 5 ml of perchloric acid (HClO₄). The addition of these acids may be repeated where there is no clear solution, which indicated that the digestion is incomplete. They were heated at 90°C ± 5°C on a hot plate for about 20 minutes until the sample is almost completely dry. To these samples were then added another 10 ml of 4M HCl and warmed for about 5 – 10 minutes to ensure complete homogeneity of the solution after which it was removed from the hot plate and left to cool. Standards for each elements were also prepared in the same way.

The digested samples were then filtered one after the other; and the filtrate were transferred into a 100 mL standard measuring cylinder. Distilled water was then added to dilute the filtrate to the 100 mL mark. These were then poured into clean sample bottles, tightly locked with cover and kept inside refrigerator to prevent decomposition. These samples were later analysed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer to determine the total heavy metals concentration in each sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physical parameters were okay for all the borehole water samples. All the samples were colourless, odourless and clear. None was turbid, damp or cloudy. Their pH were within 6.3 to 6.9. Their ECs were within 200 – 800 µS/cm, even though WHO permissible limit is up to 2,500 µS/cm. Their total dissolved solids (TDS) were also okay; none exceed 300 ppm which is considered as safe limit; while their alkalinities were within acceptable limit. None exceed 200 mg/L as CaCO₃. Most heavy metals required for growth and healthy development in living things are generally required in small quantities, usually in micrograms per kilogramme in human beings; and even other animals and plants. Their sources are mainly through food that we consume and water; which we drink or use in preparing or cooking them. Since these elements are required in micro quantities, there are points at which they become dangerous when consumed indiscriminately and become severally accumulated in the body organs; which is known as bioaccumulation and results in these substances exceeding the acceptable limits set by reputable organisation such as World Health Organisation (WHO), United State Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and many others.

Table 3: Some World Acceptable/Tolerable Limits For Heavy Metals Under Study

Standards	Cd	Cr	Co	Cu	Fe	Pb	Mn	Ni	Zn
WHO	0.003	0.05	0.01	2.00	0.30	0.010	0.40	0.07	3.00
USEPA	0.005	0.01	—	1.30	0.30	0.015	5.00	0.10	5.00
NESREA	0.003	0.05	0.005	1.00	0.30	0.010	0.20	0.02	3.00

Table 3 shows the tolerable limits for the heavy metals under study. The table shows the acceptable limit from three different agencies or organisation. They are the World Health Organisation (WHO), United State Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) and National Environmental Standard and Regulatory Agency (NESREA); which is saddled with such responsibility in Nigeria.

Table 4: Result Of Total Heavy Metals Concentration From Borehole Water Samples From COEW Wells (ppm)

SN	SAMPLE CODE	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
1	CWBW-1	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.066	3.406	<0.001	0.048	0.026	0.078
2	CWBW-2	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.82	1.294	<0.001	0.065	7.82	1.18
3	CWBW-3	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.066	2.779	<0.001	0.126	0.864	0.102
4	CWBW-4	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.104	3.914	<0.001	0.004	0.243	0.138
5	CWBW-5	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.114	3.836	<0.001	0.188	0.142	0.082
6	CWBW-6	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	1.22	1.275	<0.001	0.053	5.24	0.96
7	CWBW-7	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	1.58	0.733	<0.001	0.052	11.44	1.88
8	CWBW-8	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	1.6	4.628	<0.001	0.048	7.12	1.64
9	CWBW-9	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.14	2.91	<0.001	0.067	5.04	1.86
10	CWBW-10	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.28	0.479	<0.001	0.055	2.38	1.94

The result for the analyses of total heavy metals concentration in the borehole water samples from College of Education Warri which represent Warri metropolis is as presented in Table 4. From the result, Cd, Cr, Co and Mn were below detectable limits; which is less than 0.001 ppm. Cu ranged from .066 – 2.28 ppm; with CWBW-10 having the highest value (2.28 ppm) and CWBW-1 having the lowest value (.066 ppm). Based on the various standards, samples 9 and 10 exceed WHO acceptable limit. Samples 7 to 10 exceed USEPA acceptable limit; while samples 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 exceed NESREA set standard. This shows that Cu concentrations in some samples from Warri axis need to be controlled. Fe ranged from .479 – 4.528 ppm; with CWBW-8 having the highest value (4.628 ppm) and CWBW-10 having the lowest value (.479 ppm). The acceptable limit of Fe for all the three standards used in this study is .30 ppm, implying that the Fe in all the samples are above the recommended base line, which is .30 ppm. Iron contamination is so high and has to be treated for all the boreholes water. Even the lowest value, which is sample CWBW-10 is multiple times higher than the permissible limit.

For nickel (Ni), it ranged from .004 – 188 ppm; with samples 3 and 5 having the highest values (.126 and .188 ppm). These values exceed the acceptable limits for all the three standards. Eight samples met WHO standard which is .07 ppm; while all the ten samples did not meet NESREA standard, which is .02 ppm; which is regarded as Nigeria standard. This implies that all the boreholes water need to be treated before using so as to ensure that the Ni values are within the acceptable range; and also to prevent any future health complications. The values for Pb ranged from .026 – 11.44 ppm. Lead is a metal with health concern when present in high quantity. Unfortunately these values are alarming since the acceptable limit is .01 to .015 ppm for all the standards. Lead presence is probably due to anthropogenic reasons since the topography of these areas are water logged which allows easy leaching. The study shows that all the boreholes water need treatment before they can be used for domestic, drinking or other purposes because there is the need to prevent future health problems such as plumbism. Zinc values ranged from .078 – 1.94 ppm; with samples 2, 7, 8, 9 and 10 having high values; all greater than 1 ppm. While samples 1, 3, 4 and 5 are having lower values of less than one. Comparing them with the various standards, they are all within the acceptable limits; thus zinc concentrations in the boreholes water are very acceptable.

Table 5: Result Of Total Heavy Metals Concentration From Borehole Water Samples From COEM Wells (ppm)

SN	SAMPLE CODE	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
1	CMBW-1	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	1.94	2.121	<0.001	0.057	10.34	0.78
2	CMBW-2	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.38	4.538	<0.001	0.068	7.70	1.14
3	CMBW-3	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.06	1.424	<0.001	0.046	4.94	1.10
4	CMBW-4	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.50	1.667	<0.001	0.054	9.42	1.40
5	CMBW-5	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.04	2.222	<0.001	0.052	11.30	0.78
6	CMBW-6	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.42	3.023	<0.001	0.055	8.40	0.80
7	CMBW-7	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	1.84	3.823	<0.001	0.076	9.02	1.22
8	CMBW-8	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.22	4.619	<0.001	0.045	3.24	0.66
9	CMBW-9	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.38	6.008	<0.001	0.043	8.82	1.60
10	CMBW-10	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	2.38	2.153	<0.001	0.056	7.22	1.32

In the next presentation, the result for the analyses of total heavy metals concentration in the borehole water samples from Ethiopie axis which College of Education Mosogar boreholes water samples represent is as displayed in Table 5. From the result, it is obvious that Cd, Cr, Co and Mn were also below detectable limits; that is less than .001 ppm, hence they do not pose any danger or hazard when consumed or used for domestic, drinking or other purposes. Cu ranged from 1.84 – 2.38 ppm. All the values are above the permissible limits for USEPA and NESREA standards. In addition, samples 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9 and 10 have values above permissible limit for WHO, which is 2.0 ppm. The values for Fe ranged from 1.424 – 6.008 ppm; with CMBW-9 having the highest value (6.008 ppm) and CMBW-3 having the lowest value (1.424 ppm). The acceptable limit of Fe for all the standard is .30 ppm; this implies that the Fe in all the samples are above the recommended base line. Iron concentration is much higher in COEM samples. This transform to higher contamination of water from these boreholes, hence the need to treat these boreholes before using for any purpose, especially for drinking and domestic aspect.

Nickel (Ni) concentration in the COEM samples ranged from .043 – .076 ppm; with samples 7 and 2 having the highest values (.076 and .068 ppm respectively). Sample 7 value exceed the acceptable limits for WHO and NESREA standards; while all the remaining nine samples fulfilled the WHO and NESREA acceptable standards. All the samples are above the USEPA set standard, which is .10 ppm. The implication is that water from these boreholes also need to be properly treated before putting into use so as to ensure that the Ni quantity in these boreholes are not harmful to consumers. The values for lead ranged from 3.24 – 11.30 ppm. Lead is a metal that has devastating effects in the body. Hence, the health concern for excess Pb in the body has been on for a while; thus these values are alarming since the acceptable limit for WHO is .01 ppm, USEPA is .015 ppm and NESREA is .01 ppm. The alarming values indicated that the COEM formations were probably used in the past for activities involving Pb, which resulted in Pb accumulation in the formations due to leaching and other processes. The study shows that all the water from these boreholes need comprehensive treatment before they can be put into use so as to prevent health disaster. Zinc values ranged from .66 – 1.60 ppm; with samples 9, 4, 10 and 3 in decreasing order having high values; which is greater than 1 ppm. While the values for other samples are below 1.0 ppm. The values are okay because they are all below the maximum threshold for the three standards which ranged from 3.0 to .5.0 ppm. Hence, the zinc concentrations in the water of these boreholes are very satisfying and are safe for drinking domestic and other purposes.

CONCLUSION

Water sustain life because it is something that cannot be avoided when it comes to food chain. It is an essential food to the body; it is a force through which essential minerals some of which are heavy metals

are pumped into the body in micro quantities; and it is a means through which the body can be damaged when wrong quantity such as excess minerals or heavy metals are released into the body through it. From the results, it is obvious that Cd, Co, Cr and Mn pose no danger for all the samples from Warri and Ethiope axis. Because the outcome indicated low levels of these metals, they were found to be below detectable limit. However, it is not the same for other heavy metals investigated. Values obtained for copper is generally lower for Warri axis compare to Mosogar axis. Most of the samples from COEM are having Cu concentrations above WHO, USEPA and NESREA standards. Which shows that Cu concentrations are on the verge of becoming very undesirable hence water from these boreholes need serious attention to reduce Cu concentrations in them. The result is even more undesirable for iron. None of the twenty samples analysed passed for permissible limit for Fe for any of the standards, which is .30 ppm. The good news is that Fe concentration is generally tolerated by human bodies. Minimum value obtained for Fe in all the samples is .479 ppm, which is even higher than value recommended in all the standards.

Nickel is concentration is okay for WHO and USEPA, but above permissible level for NESREA. Using WHO and USEPA permissible levels, one can say that Ni concentrations are generally okay for both drinking and domestic purposes. Lead total concentrations are also alarming. The values obtained were exponentially above the standards; which is .01 ppm for both WHO and NESREA; and .015 ppm for USEPA. While the lowest value obtained for all the samples was 0.026 ppm, which is even higher. Pb found in this level point to either anthropogenic factors or fast bioaccumulation in the soil due to nature of the soil. Pb being a dangerous substance, sometimes, even in minute quantity, shows the need for these boreholes water to be treated before usage. Values obtained for zinc values were very okay. They were all below the permissible limits for all the standards. In general, values obtained for Warri axis were better than those obtained from Mosogar axis in terms of the three standards used for all the heavy metals. Result also shows that Pb values are dangerously higher than others heavy metals. In all, the order of concentration for both zones are Pb > Fe > Cu > Zn > Ni; while the tolerable limits are in the reverse. Also there should be more focus on the treatment of water from boreholes coded CWBW-2, CWCB-7 AND CWCW-8 for Warri axis; and CMCW-1, CMCW-5 and CMCW-9 for Mosogar axis before using for any purpose. In conclusion, the water from the tested boreholes raise more concern in terms of the concentrations of some heavy metals in focus, hence the need for public enlightenment; and there is the need to treat most of them before using for any purpose, especially for drinking, domestic and scientific usage. This is to prevent future health problems which can be as a result of bioaccumulation in the body; and to prevent any form of health and environmental disaster.

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